

Rethinking housing as a kit-of-parts and shearing layers: An LCA approach

Annette Davis¹ and Alberto Quintana Gallardo²

¹ School of Architecture La Salle, Ramon Llull University, Spain

² School of Architecture, Universitat Politècnica de València, Spain

Keywords: life cycle assessment, shearing layers, design for disassembly, industrialised construction, kit-of-parts

1. Introduction

Our built environment generates many climate challenges and at the forefront to address these are decarbonisation, implementing regenerative principles, and the transition to a Circular Economy (ARUP, 2016; EMF, 2015). As 75% of building stock in the EU is residential (EC, 2022), focusing on housing is key to responding to these issues.

Carbon emissions in housing can be reduced over the building lifespan using strategies such as Design for Disassembly (DfD) and Industrialised Construction (IC), with the planned reuse of building components, known as a kit-of-parts. Shearing Layers is similar concept that treats buildings as layers and components, which can be utilised to improve the circularity of housing.

Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) is used to quantify the environmental impacts of buildings (EC, 2010). However, the conventional LCA methodology does not support the use of these innovative construction approaches, in addition to a current lack of guidance over the replacement of different building elements.

The aim of this study is to propose an LCA methodology that supports a circular approach to housing and the replacement of building components. The kit-of-parts and Shearing Layers concepts were applied a case study house, to investigate the impact these theoretical assumptions have on carbon emissions during a 100-year lifespan.

1.1 Housing as a kit-of-parts

A kit-of-parts approach to housebuilding breaks down the home into a library of separate standardised and pre-engineered components, much like a LEGO set (Howe et al., 1999). Large building elements such as wall panels, roofs, and bathroom pods are considered products that can be mass customised to provide different housing configurations. Production is made economically viable using economies of scale through IC, also known as Modern Methods of Construction (MMC), which commonly takes place off-site under controlled factory conditions (Andersson & Lessing, 2017).

Circular housing requires repairing, reusing, remanufacturing, and recycling building components over the course of the lifecycle, both during the use phase (whilst the home is inhabited) and at the end of its useful life. These processes rely on DfD to safely remove building elements whilst avoiding damage to other building parts, which would otherwise result in greater carbon emissions (Crowther, 2005; Cruz Rios & Grau, 2019).

1.2 Housing as shearing layers

Another approach to housebuilding is Shearing Layers, a concept created by Duffy (1992) and further developed by Brand (1994), which conceptualises buildings through six layers, these are the Site, Skin (façade), Structure, Services, Space plan (partitions and fittings), and Stuff (furnishings). Each of these have differing expected lifespans and hence require different frequencies of replacement. The recent European-wide framework Level(s) incorporates this concept within indicator 1.2 for Global Warming Potential, to provide users with metrics for component lifespans to perform an LCA (Dodd & Donatello, 2020).

1.3 Life cycle assessment

LCA is a methodology and decision-supporting tool used by industry professionals and scholars to measure and compare the environmental impacts of buildings. LCAs are based on the international standard EN 15978 that consists of phases A-D, covering the product and construction phase (A), use (B), demolition (C), and beyond end-of-life benefits (D). There is ongoing research into utilising LCA to combine the Shearing Layers concept to measure the impacts of building components (Densley Tingley & Davison, 2012; Joensuu et al., 2022; Pushkar & Verbitsky, 2014). Nevertheless, there lacks a robust LCA methodology outlining the replacement of kit-of-parts components.

2. Methods

2.1 Research framework

This study applied the kit-of-parts and Shearing Layers concepts to housing, to break down the building into manageable elements and measure their environmental impacts using LCA. The LCA methodology used was based on the international standard illustrated in Figure 1, measuring carbon emissions of kit-of-parts components over the product and construction phases (A1-A5) and parts of the use phase over a 100-year period including: replacement (B4), operational energy (B6) and water (B7) usage.

Figure 1. Building life cycle phases and modules. Source: Author's own image based on EN 15978

A kit-of-parts was organised into four of Brand's (1994) Shearing Layers: the structure, skin, services, and space plan; the stuff and site were considered out of the scope of this study. The lifespan of each layer was based on values provided by the Level(s) framework (Dodd & Donatello, 2020), with the exception of the structure. As illustrated in Figure 2, over a 100-year period, the structure would be built once, the skin replaced every 30 years, the services every 25 years, and the space plan every 20 years.

Figure 2. Shearing Layers and assumed life spans. Source: Author's own image based on Brand (1994) and Dodd & Donatello (2020)

2.2 A Case study: Single family house

Edificación Eco-Eficiente (E3) served as a case study to apply the LCA, a prototype house built in 2011 at the UPV campus in Valencia, Spain. Prominent characteristics are the steel structure, ventilated ceramic façade, and photovoltaics on the roof to produce on-site renewable energy. Built using industrialised methods, the house was prefabricated and assembled on-site within 19 days. Although E3 was not designed using a kit-of-parts or the Shearing Layers concept, the Bill of Quantities could be organised into assumed kit-of-parts components and subsequently into the four separate layers.

2.3 Analysis tools and methods

SimaPro was used to perform the analysis of materials and processes in conjunction with the ecoinvent Life Cycle Inventory database. Materials were adapted to the availability of European suppliers, to support the comparison of future case studies from different European countries. The annual energy consumption was provided from a previous study by the Centre for Physics Technologies at UPV, and water consumption was assumed as the Spanish national average.

3. Results and discussion

The LCA revealed which building layers emit the most carbon, whilst the kit-of-parts enabled identification of which components should be re-designed to reduce environmental impacts. The carbon emissions due to replacement (B4) of the skin, services, and space plan over the 100-year period were greater than the total embodied energy to produce and construct the original building (A1-A5). The results also show E3 is a positive energy building, however, it is not net-positive energy within the 100 years. This means more embodied energy was spent to

produce the building and replace parts, than the amount of energy produced by the photovoltaics.

4. Conclusion

The assumed lifespan of building elements has a significant impact on carbon emissions over the building lifespan. Assumptions based on the kit-of-parts and Shearing Layers concepts were applied, highlighting the importance to strike the right balance between prolonged periods of the useful life of building parts, and their planned replacement. This work is being further developed as part of the on-going doctoral research with RE-DWELL.

Acknowledgment

The work presented in this publication has been carried out within the RE-DWELL Innovative Training Network, funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement no. 956082. This work has been developed with the support of Professor Ignacio Guillén.

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